

The Frequency Of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Among School Age Children Of Rawalpindi

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Abstract

Background: Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is mainly defined by features of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. It is the most frequently encountered childhood-onset neurodevelopmental disorder in the primary care settings.

Objective: The objective of this study is to determine the prevalence of Attention Deficit Hyperkinetic Disorder (ADHD) in school going children of Rawalpindi.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out from May 2017 to July 2018 in schools of Rawalpindi. Our study population comprised of children and teens with age ranging from 6-16. A standard questionnaire 'Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fourth Edition Teachers' Version' (DSM-IV-TR) was used to collect information from 223 teachers about the children.

Results: Out of 223 study subjects, 105 (47.0%) were male and 118 (52.9%) were females with mean age of 12 years. Out of the total sample, 77 (34.5%) were diagnosed with ADHD. Out of these 77, we found out that 41 (53.2%) were suffering from ADHD-I (inattention) making it the most prevalent sub-type of the ADHD in the given sample, whereas 18 (23.3%) children were found out to be suffering from ADHD-HI (hyperactivity) and 18 (23.3%) from ADHD-C (combined) type.

Conclusion: The prevalence of ADHD is much higher in our population than in most regions of the world indicating negligence towards this important psychiatric problem.

Key Words: Attention Deficit Hyperkinetic Disorder, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fourth Edition, School children

Introduction

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is mainly defined by features of inattention, overactivity,

and impulsivity. It is the most frequently encountered childhood-onset neurodevelopmental disorder in the primary care settings.¹ This disorder is manifested as age-inappropriate distractibility, reduced attention span, and overactivity across different settings.² It often has a chronic course and persists into adulthood in many individuals. In addition, it may have clinically important effects on the health-related quality of life in children, the emotional health of parents, and the activities/cohesion of families.³

Attention Deficit Hyperkinetic Disorder (ADHD) has deleterious effects on school-aged children. It results in restlessness, impulsive acts, and lack of focus, which may impair school performance.^{4,5} At school, students with ADHD are often inattentive, disorganized, off-task and disruptive which often leads to low rates of work completion both in class and at home.^{6,7} Children with ADHD also exhibit a variety of peer-related problems including overly intrusive and negative peer interactions⁸ which can be further exacerbated by associated aggression, argumentativeness, disruptiveness, and lack of self-control.⁹ It is noted from a study that almost half of the children with ADHD were diagnosed before the age of six years old. In other studies, symptoms of ADHD may have been diagnosed before the age of six years old. And there were cases noted of late-onset ADHD in some studies. ADHD may affect not only children less than 6 years old, but even those up to 18 years old.¹⁰ Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is the most common mental and behavioural disorder for school-age children.¹¹

A debate exists as to whether ADHD might be a cultural construct.¹²⁻¹⁴ The opinion that geographic location may influence the epidemiology of ADHD and attention deficit hyperactivity symptoms persist despite findings to the contrary in a few studies that culture and geographic location may have little to no influence on the epidemiology of ADHD worldwide.¹⁵ Linnet noted an unconfirmed link between socioeconomic factors and ADHD in children.¹⁶ This was confirmed by Zwirs and colleagues who

suggested that additional research is needed to conclusively test whether socioeconomic class is a risk factor for ADHD in at least some populations.¹⁷ However, Dopfner and colleagues noted a higher prevalence in families of lower socioeconomic status and families from urban areas.¹⁸

The diagnosis of ADHD is complicated by the frequent occurrence of comorbid conditions, such as learning disability, conduct disorder, and anxiety disorder. Symptoms of these conditions may also mimic ADHD. The diagnosis of ADHD depends heavily on parent and teacher reports, and no laboratory tests can reliably predict ADHD.¹⁹

This study investigated the frequency and pattern of ADHD in school going children. Our hope is that this study will shed light on ADHD in a school setting, so that we can assess the frequency of ADHD among school going children. It is not only estimating problem occurrence but the sensitization of the concerned and remedial measures that can benefit in any way.

Studies on the topic of ADHD in Pakistan are not available in abundance. Such studies are essential for the formulation of policies on intervention and delivery of better educational services. This study will help to determine if there is a difference in the frequency of ADHD diagnosed in various different socio-economic standards and school settings. In addition, this study will establish baseline patterns of distribution of ADHD and will assist physicians, who have a high index of suspicion, to diagnose ADHD. The objective of this study is to determine the frequency of ADHD in school going children of Rawalpindi.

Patients and Methods

This cross-sectional study was carried out in from May 2017 to July 2018, in Rawalpindi, Pakistan. Our study population comprised of children and teens with age ranging from 6-16, studying in various educational institutions all over the city. The institutions included were both private and government sector. Five institutions were included and sample size was divided as 48 students each school by simple random sampling. Informed consent was taken by the heads of each academic institution before initiation of study. Using an anticipated proportion of 0.18, 95% confidence interval and 6% absolute precision, minimally required sample size according to WHO sample size calculator was calculated to be 210, however, 240 participants were included.

A structured self-administered questionnaire 'Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fourth Edition' (DSM-IV-TR) was used to collect information from the teachers of children who belonged to various schools throughout the city, during the study period. Teachers were asked to provide information regarding their gender, ethnic group, number of years of teaching experience, type of classroom, and grade level taught. In a few cases where the teachers were unclear on various questions or had an issue with the language (since English is not the national language), the questionnaire was administered by study investigators.

This scale is an 18-item questionnaire that requires the respondent to rate the frequency of occurrence of ADHD symptoms as defined by the DSM-IV-TR (Approved by American Psychiatric Association 2000). Teacher version of this scale was used. Ratings of behaviour on the ADHD-Rating Scale-IV were collected on students aged 6 to 16 years. Teachers completed two to six rating scales on students chosen randomly by the investigator from the class roster. The respondent (questionnaire was filled by teachers) rates each item on a Likert scale of 0 (not at all) to 3 (very often). The total score of the questionnaire is 54, the cut off values are 12 for inattention, hyperactivity and combined type. The scale yields scores for an Inattentive, Hyperactive/Impulsive and Total Scale. A total of 240 questionnaires were distributed out of which 223 were filled appropriately producing a response rate of 92.9%. To assess the socioeconomic status both government and private schools were selected as in our society mostly the children belonging to lower socioeconomic status study in government and those belonging to middle and upper class study in private institutions.

Our results were concluded after getting data forms filled by teachers of various academic institutions. Data was entered in entered in Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS version 22). For all the categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were calculated whereas for continuous variables, means, median and standard deviations were computed.

Results

A total of 240 questionnaires were included ranging from 6-16 years (Mean 12.49 years), out of which the response of 223 was adequate for the study, producing a response rate of 92.9%.

Out of the total sample, 77 (34.5%) were diagnosed with ADHD. Out of these 77, we found out that 41

(53.2%) were suffering from ADHD-I (inattention) making it the most prevalent sub-type of the ADHD in the given sample, whereas 18 (23.3%) children were found out to be suffering from ADHD-HI (hyperactivity) and 18 (23.3%) from ADHD-C (combined) type.

Among the selected population sample, 105 (47.0%) were male and 118 (52.9%) were females. Out of these, 33 (31.4%) males and 44 (37.3%) females were diagnosed with ADHD. In order to assess the effect of socio-economic status 23 (36.5%) children from the government and 54 (33.8%) from the private sector were diagnosed with ADHD.

Table I: Distribution of ADHD by age groups, gender and school type in the population examined

Total (n=223)		Normal (n=146)	ADHD (n=77)
Age groups	≤ 10 yrs (n=41)	19 (46.3%)	22 (53.6%)
	>10 yrs (n=182)	127 (69.8%)	55 (30.2%)
Gender	Male (n=105)	72 (68.6%)	33 (31.4%)
	Female (n=118)	74 (62.7%)	44 (37.3%)
School Setup	Government (n=63)	40 (63.5%)	23 (36.5%)
	Private (n=160)	106 (66.3%)	54 (33.8%)

Table II Frequency of different types of ADHD among age, gender and school in population examined

Total (n=223)		ADHD (n=77)		
		ADHD-I (n=41)	ADHD-HI (n=18)	ADHD-C (n=18)
Age groups	≤ 10 yrs (n=41)	6 (14.6%)	10 (24.4%)	6 (14.6%)
	>10 yrs (n=182)	35 (19.2%)	8 (4.4%)	12 (6.6%)
Gender	Male (n=105)	15 (14.3%)	10 (9.5%)	8 (7.6%)
	Female (n=118)	26 (22.0%)	8 (6.8%)	10 (8.5%)
School Setup	Government (n=63)	15 (23.8%)	4 (6.3%)	4 (6.3%)
	Private (n=160)	26 (16.3%)	14 (8.8%)	14 (8.8%)

Table III Percentage of students with ADHD by grade level

CLASS	TOTAL	ADHD (n with %)
Grade 3	23	6 (7.8)
Grade 4	22	8(10.4)

Grade 5	12	8(10.4)
Grade 6	23	9(11.7)
Grade 7	56	19(24.7)
Grade 8	26	10(12.9)
Grade 9	31	9(11.7)
Grade 10	30	8(10.4)

FIGURE I: Graph showing the frequency of ADHD in private and government school setups

FIGURE II: Graph showing the frequency of different subtypes of ADHD in age groups

Discussion

ADHD is the most common neurobehavioral diagnosis affecting children in the world today. It interferes with the student's education, quality of life and ability to be productive members of society as they grow older. After parents and teachers, the most likely professional to encounter children with ADHD is the medical provider.²⁰

We performed this study in various schools of Rawalpindi, including both private and government sector, having both genders with a wide age group of school going children ranging from 6 to 16 years of age. Our study found out a total incidence of 34.5% among the selected participants. Even though this proportion was much higher than that encountered in

the west and other eastern countries, it corresponds to another study conducted in Karachi, according to which the prevalence of ADHD was calculated to be 34% in children.²¹ The results of ADHD frequency in other countries were much lesser than ours, for instance, frequency of ADHD in Saudi Arabian primary schools is reported to be as low as 2.7%²², while that in Iran is reported to be as high as 13%²³ and that in USA it is as high as 16%²⁴

Although the causes of the variability in ADHD prevalence worldwide are unknown, geographic and demographic factors have been implicated.^[25] A debate exists as to whether ADHD might be a cultural construct. The opinion that geographic location may influence the epidemiology of ADHD and attention deficit hyperactivity symptoms persists despite findings to the contrary in a few studies that culture and geographic location may have little to no influence on the epidemiology of ADHD worldwide^[15] Our results could be different from other countries because of the difference of the social and cultural norms. Also, Pakistan is a developing country where such psychological problems are usually ignored, which is one of the reasons why we could not find much ADHD studies in Pakistan apart from a couple.

When we compared the results of the frequency in gender, our results were different from the results of most studies where a male preponderance has been noted.¹⁰ It is seen from the results of our study that the frequency was higher in females (37.3%) compared to the males (31.4%) who had a relatively lower frequency. It is confirmed by a similar study where frequency of ADHD was higher in girls. One remote possibility is that increase in the usage of social media (particularly among young girls) may have resulted in an increase in ADHD incidence in girls, since boys are more commonly indulged in outdoor activities. Research also indicates that the increasing use of social media may place children at greater risk for psychiatric problems and suicide; young girls, because of their social nature, may be at particular high risk.²⁶ Future work, however, is needed to confirm such speculations.

Our study indicated that there were more children affected by ADHD that were less than 10 years of age (53.6%) than those who were older than 10 years (30.2%). Most of the studies showed that children were less than 10 years when they were diagnosed of ADHD.

Some scholars also observed that as age increases, symptoms of attention deficits remain relatively stable and hyperactivity symptoms are gradually reduced.²⁷

Moreover, it has been reported that up to 98% of individuals diagnosed with ADHD during childhood no longer meet criteria for a diagnosis of ADHD at follow up seven to eight years later.²⁸ That might be the reason why most of our subjects reported with a higher ADHD prevalence at a younger age. In some studies, there were cases noted of late-onset ADHD. ADHD may affect not only children less than 6 years old, but even those up to 18 years old.¹⁰

Most of the children in our research with ADHD belonged to private schools than government setups. Our studies showed that frequency in private setups was higher (36.5%) while frequency was low in government schools (33.8%). In our society, children studying in private schools come from middle and high socioeconomic classes while those studying in government schools mostly belong to low socioeconomic class. The reason for the higher frequency of ADHD in private schools in our research may be because most of our data was collected from private schools as their teachers were more compliant. Studies in some countries have indicated that individuals from low socioeconomic class environments are 1.5-4 times more likely to meet criteria for ADHD than individuals from families from high socioeconomic classes.¹⁷ However other studies have not found a significant relationship between socioeconomic class and the prevalence of ADHD.²⁹ In our study, we had more children with ADHD-I (53.2%) than with ADHD-HI (23.3%) or ADHD-C (23.3%). This was confirmed by Erik in his study where he noted a high frequency of ADHD-I among children with ADHD.³⁰ This was also corroborated by a Nigerian study.³¹ In addition, in the US, children diagnosed with ADHD, when reassessed each year for eight years, were more likely to shift to a different subtype of ADHD.¹⁶

Conclusion

The frequency of ADHD is much higher in our population than in most regions of the world indicating negligence towards this important yet often ignored psychiatric problem. This extreme frequency of ADHD among our young population is alarming and can lead to severe functional impairment as an adult. More study is required to be conducted in our region and adequate measures are to be taken to eradicate this serious problem.

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